

The RespTrack system

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This paper describes the RespTrack system for measuring and real-time monitoring of respiratory movements. RespTrack was developed in the Phonetics Laboratory at Stockholm University and the authors have been using it extensively for research for the past five years. Here, we describe briefly the underlying techniques, calibration, digitization as well as recent developments of the system. The presentation at SEFOS 2019 will also include a live demonstration of the system.

INTRODUCTION

RespTrack is a system for measuring and monitoring respiratory movements using the Respiratory Inductance Plethysmography (RIP) method [1,2].

Very briefly, the RIP method uses two elastic inductive belts placed around the rib cage and around the abdomen. Respiratory movements—inhalations and exhalations—alter the inductance of the belts. The belts are connected to electronics that convert the varying inductance into an analog signal with an amplitude that is proportional to the changes in lung volume. This signal can be digitized and recorded and/or displayed in real-time. There is general consensus that RIP is the most frequently used, established and accurate plethysmography method to monitor respiratory movements [3,4].

The RespTrack system is a recent incarnation of the RIP method developed in the Stockholm University Phonetics Laboratory by Peter Branderud and Johan Stark. RespTrack was commissioned by Mattias Heldner and it has been used extensively for research by Marcin Włodarczak and Mattias Heldner (with colleagues) for the last five years [5-23]. About ten RespTrack systems have also been made available to colleagues outside Stockholm University and are being used for research in several different disciplines (e.g. phonetics, voice science, speech and language pathology, ENT medicine). A second batch of RespTrack systems will be available during the fall 2019.

This paper gives a brief description of the the system, including recent developments and describes how we calibrate and digitize the signals from the system. The presentation at SEFOS 2019 will also include a live demonstration of the system.

SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

RespTrack was designed for ease of use, and optimized for low noise and low interference recordings of respiratory movements in speech and singing. The system consists of (i) two elastic inductive belts, (ii) a main unit, and (iii) a cable to connect the belts to the main unit. Fig. 1 shows the components of the system.

Fig. 1. RespTrack main unit, inductance belts and cable.

The main unit has one combined input for the rib cage (RC) and abdomen (AB) belts connection cable and three analog signal outputs: RC, AB, and “+” a weighted sum of the RC and AB signals allowing a direct estimation of lung volume change. All connections are made with mechanically robust connectors (input TA4F mini XLR, outputs BNC). The range of the output signals is $\pm 2V$. The main unit automatically turns on when it is connected to an inductive belt. This is indicated by LEDs (one per belt) that also serve as battery indicators.

One important ease-of-use aspect of RespTrack is the possibility to control the contribution of the individual belts to the weighted sum, which is done by means of a potentiometer knob on the main unit. This is used to ensure that a given volume of air in the lungs produce the same summed output irrespective of how that volume is distributed between the rib cage and abdominal compartments. A slightly higher weight to the RC belt is usually required [24], we have found that a setting of about +2.5 on the RespTrack potentiometer knob is a good starting point for most speakers. Correct weighting of the belts is obtained by instructing the subject to close the glottis, and then to repeatedly contract and relax the abdominal wall, while the experimenter adjusts the potentiometer so that the summed signal remains flat when air is moved from the belly to the rib cage. This is the so called *isovolume manouver* [25].

Another ease-of-use aspect is the possibility of correcting DC offset simultaneously for the RC and AB belts using a “reset” button on the main unit. This function is very practical to get signals within range to be displayed on screen, but it is also used to obtain a meaningful “zero line” in respiratory recordings. Typically, the subject is instructed to produce a relaxed sigh. The experimenter then presses the reset button just after the sigh. A zero reading will then correspond to the resting point of the elastic rib cage and lungs. This resting point is usually referred to as the resting expiratory level or REL [26]. The REL point is relevant in breathing studies as people generally seem to avoid going below REL and many inhalations are initiated around REL.

Furthermore, the reset button alleviates the need for the high-pass filter (HPF) for direct current (DC) offset removal found in many other RIP systems. More importantly, the *absence* of a HPF for DC removal in RespTrack permits the study of certain types of interesting breathing phenomena that cannot be captured in many other systems. For example, periods of breath-holding can be distinguished from slow exhalations with RespTrack, whereas they are indistinguishable in systems including such a HPF for DC removal. This can easily be tested by verifying that the signal remains constant during a breath-hold.

If needed, the weighted sum channel in the RIP recordings can be calibrated in liters using either a “spiromat” with a known volume, or a digital spirometer (e.g. CareFusion MicroLoop). In the latter case, we typically ask the subject to perform a vital capacity maneuver and use the inspirational capacity (i.e. REL to maximum inhalation) reported by the spirometer for calibration.

INDUCTIVE BELTS

In our previous work, we have used commercially available RIP transducer belts (Ambu RIP-mate, pediatric size). We are currently evaluating prototypes of new belts developed by Peter Branderud and Johan Stark which promise several advantages. From a practical point of view, they are much easier to mount and to adjust in size. This is due to a different wiring of the coils in the belts and a simplified cable connection. The new belts are also considerably less susceptible to interference from other systems used in parallel (e.g. other RIP systems or EGG).

SAFETY

The RespTrack system is electrically very safe to use due to its design. Firstly, the main unit is only supplied by low voltage power sources, two AA 1.5V batteries, or an USB connection. Secondly the inductive belts that are worn by the subjects are connected to the electronics via isolation transformers and high impedance resistors in the connection cable.

DIGITIZING THE RIP SIGNALS

The hardware requirements for digitizing slowly varying signals such as respiratory movements captured by RIP exclude the use of normal soundcards that typically have a frequency response of 20 Hz to 20 kHz. We have used different combinations of hardware and software.

In most of our published studies, we have used an integrated data acquisition system for recording the RIP signals (PowerLab hardware and LabChart software by ADInstruments). This system was quite expensive but allowed us to simultaneously record three RespTrack systems in parallel as well as to get started quickly.

Johan Stark has also developed a LabVIEW application—RTRecorder—for use with data acquisition hardware from National Instruments (e.g. USB-6000). RTRecorder records 3 RIP signals, stereo audio signals and a sync signal. See Fig. 2 for a screen shot of RTRecorder.

Most recently, we have been experimenting with hardware intended for the modular synthesizer world (Expert Sleepers ES-8, ES-7 and ES-6). These Eurorack modules in combination provide a USB audio interface with 12 input channels that can be used both for audio and RIP signals due to its DC coupled inputs. A distinct advantage is that the cost of this system is a fraction of the integrated system we have been using in the past. Recording can be done with standard digital audio workstation (DAW) software.

Fig. 2. Screen shot of RTRecorder.

ANALYZING THE RIP SIGNALS

With respect to analysis of RIP signals, the second author has developed RespInPeace, a Python toolkit for pre-processing and analysis of the respiratory signal [27]. The library implements procedures related to, among others, signal normalization and calibration (drift removal, estimation of respiratory range, etc.), respiratory cycle segmentation, identification of respiratory holds, and extraction of selected respiratory features. The code has been released under a free software license and is available online [28].

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